

Community Engagement Metrics

Rationale

The definition of community engagement and community partner widely differs among projects. Including CE conversations in our monthly meetings not only help us learn about Projects' CE efforts but also help us to recognize the role CE has in participatory research.

Purpose: To better understand the community engagement dynamics of RADx-UP projects in order to support the strengthening and sustainability of Public Health participatory research within and beyond RADx-UP.

Objectives:

- Prompt CE conversations and explorations among RADx UP projects.
- Facilitate spaces for introspection, self-assessment, recognition, and reporting of Projects' CE practices.
- Gather information on the relevance and advantages of CE practices for RADx UP projects.
- Identify challenges to the implementation of CE and participatory research to report it to interested groups.

CE Continuum

Outreach

- Creating new partnerships/connections specifically for the RADx-UP project.
- Revisiting former partnerships with CBOs, etc. to collaborate on the RADx-UP initiative.
- Discussing and agreeing with CP on the best ways to communicate.
- Sharing results/research findings with the community via CP

Consult

- Knowing and understanding the goals and objectives of community partners.
- Sharing and explaining the goals and objectives of the project to community partners.
- Having a continuous channel to provide/receive feedback from community partners (i.e., regular communications - in-person check-ins, meetings, email, phone calls.)
- Consulting CP on best ways to share research results with the community.

Involve

- Creating a CAB or a similar structure that includes leaders or members of the communities you are working with.
- Bringing community voices in for informing planning and decision-making (The research team is still “in charge” of the project, but community partners participated in regular project meetings).
- Using dissemination strategies proposed by community partners or developing them based on CP knowledge and experience.

Collaborate

- Developing or pivoting interventions as a response to needs identified by CPs.
- Identifying, assessing, and continuously including benefits for all collaborating partners in work plans.
- Inviting community partners to meetings with CDCC (NIH).
- Including the CP and/or communities review of data and research findings as part of the publication and dissemination process.

Shared Leadership

- Maintaining horizontal relationships among researchers and CPs. i.e. limitations and needs of both the academic and CPs shaped the project (processes, interventions, outcomes, dissemination of findings, etc.)
- Establishing long-term, sustainable relationships (Partnership goes beyond RADx-UP.)
- Data ownership is explicitly stated (DTA/DUAs between CP and academic research team.)